

TOUGHENING OF BASALT FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH A CYCLIC BUTYLENE TEREPHTHALATE MATRIX BY A NON-ISOTHERMAL PRODUCTION

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SUMMARY

The influence of the cooling rate on the crystallization is investigated for the CBT material after polymerization to PBT. From the results it is clear that a faster cooling leads to less perfect crystallization. This influence on the crystallization is linked to the mechanical properties of composites with this matrix material.

Keywords: Mechanical properties, thermoplastic composites, processing

INTRODUCTION

Cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT[®]) is a low viscosity cyclic oligoester which polymerizes, after adding a catalyst, to the better known thermoplastic polybutyleneterephthalate (PBT) [1, 2]. The combination of the low viscosity and its thermoplastic character makes the CBT resin a very promising material. It combines a rather easy impregnation, like thermosets, with the advantage of melt recyclability of a thermoplastic matrix [3, 4]. Due to the low viscosity of the CBT in its oligomeric state it can be used in RTM-like processes, which are normally reserved to thermosets [5].

An extra advantage of the CBT system is that crystallization can start during the polymerization because the polymerization can occur already at temperatures below the crystallization temperature of the polymer [6, 7]. This makes processing under the melt temperature of PBT, at one temperature during the whole process, possible with this system. This helps reducing the production cycle [8].

However, it was found that when this resin is used under isothermal processing conditions, the matrix material is much more brittle than normal PBT [9]. Due to the isothermal production process, at which simultaneous polymerization and crystallization occurs, a perfect crystal structure with few tie-molecules arises, which leads to brittleness [6, 10, 11].

It is known that the cooling rate of a polymer plays a role in the building of the crystalline structure of the polymer. This is extensively described for PBT [12, 13]. It is also shown that this difference in crystalline structure has an influence on the mechanical properties [10, 14, 15]. In this paper a new production method for pCBT

composites is designed, in order to check if a fast cooling after complete polymerization of pCBT will lead to a tougher composite.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material

CBT™ (CBT 160) used in this study is delivered by Cyclics Corporation. The material has a melting range from 130-160 °C. Before processing, the oligomers were dried overnight at 110 °C to remove residual moisture, which could interfere with the polymerization reaction. The tin-based catalyst (Fascat™ 4101, butylchlorodihydroxy-stannan) which is commercially available from Atofina Chemicals Incorporated, is a well "established" transesterification catalyst. The catalyst is already mixed with the CBT 160 when delivered. Also CBT 100 is used in this study, when a CBT without premixed catalyst is needed.

Two different reinforcements are used, both existing of basalt fibers. The first reinforcement is a basalt roving. The used roving has a linear density of 1600 tex with a filament diameter between 12 and 15 µm. The second reinforcement is a fabric, it is a balanced twill 2/2 weave with a surface density of 220 g/m².

Experimental methods

DSC measurements are performed on a Pyris-1 DSC from Perkin Elmer. For the measurements a very low amount of material (2mg) is used in standard aluminium solid state pans to limit thermal inertia. From the measured heat flow an empty pan measurement is properly subtracted, which gives the heat flow from the sample. After dividing by the sample mass and the scanning rate, heat capacities are obtained. From these heat capacities the crystallinity at each temperature can be calculated as follows:

$$w_c = \frac{\Delta h(T)}{\Delta h_{ref}(T)} \quad (1)$$

with Δh_{ref} , the reference enthalpy for PBT from the ATHAS database: $\Delta h_{ref}(T) = 82.88781 + T * 0.44591 - T^2 * 0.000882206 + T^3 * 0.000000425303$, with T in °C, and

$$\Delta h(T) = \int_T^{230^\circ C} c_p(T) - c_{pa}(T) dT \quad (2)$$

With $c_{pa}(T)$ the reference heat capacity for fully amorphous PBT.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) is used to determine the molecular weight, its distribution and the degree of conversion. The measurements were performed with a mixture of chloroform/hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP) as solvent (98/2 CHCl₃/HFIP). The flow rate was 0.8 ml/min at a temperature of 20°C. Two Waters PL HFIPgel columns were used in series. The chromatograph was connected to Waters 484 UV detector working at 254 nm. In order to relate retention time to molecular weight, a universal calibration method was applied using various polystyrene standards. For sample preparation, approximately 1 mg of matrix was dissolved in 80 µl of HFIP. After total dissolution, the solution was diluted by 4 ml of chloroform. Samples containing basalt fibres were filtered before injection.

The degree of conversion is determined from the GPC measurements and is calculated as follows:

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{A_{oli}}{A_{tot}} \quad (4)$$

with α the degree of conversion, A_{oli} the area under the oligomer peaks of the retention time curve and A_{tot} the total area under the retention time curve (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Retention time graph of a GPC measurement.

Three point bending tests are performed according to ASTM D790-84. The sample size is $80 \times 10 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^3$ using a span of 64 mm and a speed of 2mm/min.

Mode II fracture toughness tests are performed to measure the propagation strain energy release rate (kJ/m^2). The samples have a thickness of 1mm and a width of 20mm. The premade crack has a length of 25 mm and the total span is 100mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production

The production technique used for the non-isothermal production process was designed such that the polymerization does progress above the melting temperature of PBT after impregnation. After complete polymerization the composite is cooled down. It is important that during cooling a good control on the cooling rate is possible, which leads to a good control on the crystallization. Therefore a compression moulding technique is chosen. In the compression moulding equipment used, a Zenith 2 Pinette press, a good control of the cooling rate is possible. A cold stage in the press allows a very fast cooling by quenching. Two different techniques are used.

Prepreg method

The first method is used when basalt fiber rovings are used and exists of a prepreg step and the consequent compression step. For the prepregging a drumwinder is used, which is shown in Figure 2. A roving is pulled by a drum through a cylindrical resin bath which is closed at the bottom with a die. Because the resin in its powder form does not adhere to the fibers, it has to be melted in the heated resin bath. By pulling the fibers through the molten CBT, the CBT will impregnate the fiber bundles. The volume of the resin bath is very small because the molten CBT should stay only a short time in the bath, otherwise the polymerization will progress too far. After passing through the die, the yarn is rolled on a drum. By translation of the drum all the rovings are placed next to each other, resulting in a unidirectional prepreg.

Figure 2: Picture of the drumwinder, which is used for the production of the prepregs

The produced prepregs are converted into composites by compression moulding. The prepregs are heated up to 240°C and the polymerization continues. By applying a pressure of 5 bar a flat plate is produced. In order to minimize the porosity also a vacuum is applied during the compression moulding. A cooling step is performed after complete polymerization. Two different cooling rates are used, a slow cooling (-8°C/min) and a quenching (this equals -100°C/min), by transferring the material from the hot to the cold plates.

With this production technique (0,90)_s laminates are produced with a thickness of 1.5 mm and a fiber volume fraction of 43%.

Film stacking method

The second method makes use of a fabric as reinforcement. This method exists of a film making step, which are afterwards stacked in between fabrics for the compression moulding. The films are made by melting CBT and heating it up to 190°C. Then the catalyst is added and after complete mixing the polymerizing CBT is poured into different moulds. These moulds are immediately cooled down to stop the polymerization. The produced films have the same size as the mould used in the compression step.

Afterwards the fabrics and films are stacked together in the mould. With the use of a spacer, plates of 1 mm are produced, without spacers all the resin flows away.. In the compression step a pressure of 3 bar on the material is applied, while a vacuum is used to improve the impregnation. The same cooling rates are used as for the previous method. This production technique is used to produce samples for the fracture toughness test.

Process optimization

In both production processes some optimization was necessary. The polymerization temperature of 240°C was chosen because this leads to the highest molecular weight ($M_n = 24 \pm 4$ kg/mol and $M_w = 50 \pm 10$ kg/mol, the degree of conversion is 98±1%). At a lower temperature (230°C) a very low molecular weight ($M_n = 12 \pm 2$ kg/mol, $M_w = 24 \pm 3$ kg/mol) is reached. When 250°C is used for the polymerization some thermal

degradation can occur, which leads to a lower molecular weight ($M_n = 20 \pm 4$ kg/mol and $M_w = 38 \pm 10$ kg/mol, the degree of conversion is $99 \pm 1\%$).

Mechanical properties

The composites produced with the prepreg method are tested in three point bending. In the prepreg step an extra parameter occurs. Normally the drum is covered by a non-adhesive paper during prepregging. It was found that the anti-adhesive layer has probably a bad effect on the composite properties because of the worse adhesion between layers when different prepreps are stacked on top of each other for the compression moulding, leading to bad mechanical properties of the composite. To avoid this adhesion problem two different foils are used during prepregging. The mechanical properties of the composites, in which the outer layers are oriented longitudinally, are gathered in Table 1.

There is a clear difference between the slowly cooled and the quenched samples for the two types of foil used in the prepreg step. As well in strength as in failure strain and in failure mode. The stiffness of the different samples is almost the same for these samples. Three different failure modes are observed.

- **Delamination** between the layers at the tensile side of the bending specimen. This delamination initiates due to too high shear stress between the different layers. Sometimes the delamination breaks through the middle layers and grows further at the compression side.
- **Compression**, the upper layer failed by buckling because of compression.
- **Tensile**, the fibers in the lowest layer break because of the tensile stresses in that layer.

Normally all the samples should break in tensile and/or compression. However in the slowly cooled samples a delamination occurs. In the quenched, and therefore tougher, samples the matrix can resist the shear stresses and the failure is due to fiber failure (tension) or buckling of the fibers (compression).

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the composites produced with the prepreg method. The samples are tested with the 0° layers at the outside.

	Foil 1		Foil 2	
	Slow cooling	quenching	Slow cooling	quenching
E (GPa)	26 ± 1	25 ± 3	28 ± 2	28 ± 1
Strength (MPa)	220 ± 5	559 ± 56	445 ± 25	593 ± 32
Failure strain (%)	0.8 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.4
Failure method	delamination	Compression and tensile	Delamination	Compression

In the quenched samples the failure strain is for both foil 1 and 2 equal to the failure strain of basalt fibers. This means that there is really a fiber and not a matrix failure. This observation is consistent with the failure mode.

From the differences in mechanical behaviour of the produced composites it can be concluded that quenching indeed induces a higher toughness as indicated by the failure strain and the failure mode.

Fracture toughness

In order to obtain a more quantitative indication of the increase in toughness the Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is measured on slowly cooled and quenched samples. For these tests different samples are produced using the film stacking process and following the two different cooling paths.

Figure 3: SEM picture of the fracture surface of the tested composites. The basalt fibers are very dry, no matrix sticks to the fibers.

The different samples have a thickness of 1 mm and consist in 8 layers of the basalt fiber fabric. From these tests it seems that the quenching again increases the initial strain energy release rate for crack propagation, which is related to the crack propagation fracture toughness. For the slowly cooled samples this crack propagation fracture toughness is 0.04 ± 0.01 kJ/m² while for the quenched samples this value increases to 0.08 ± 0.02 kJ/m². The quenching increases the crack propagation fracture energy by 100%. These propagation values are very low, when compared to some epoxies, however this is probably due to the very poor adhesion between the pCBT and the basalt fibers (Figure 3).

Crystalline structure

An explanation for the higher toughness for the quenched samples compared to the slowly cooled samples, as demonstrated above, should be found in the crystallinity or in the perfection of the crystals. Therefore two types of DSC-measurements are performed. The first measurements are on pure pCBT using a thermal program that is designed to mimic the production cycle of the composites, while the second type of measurements are performed on the produced composites themselves.

Crystallinity of unreinforced pCBT

In these measurements unreinforced pCBT is subjected to a thermal cycle which mimics the production cycle of the composites. This means that the pCBT is subjected to the two different cooling rates to compare the difference in crystallinity between these two rates. The crystallinity is investigated during the heating, subsequent to the different coolings. Two different heating rates used, namely a slow heating (10°C/min) and a fast one (100°C/min). In the measurements during a slow heating, recrystallization can easily occur, which disturbs the results, while in the fast heated sample recrystallization is unlikely.

Measurement with slow heating

The results of the measurements with a heating rate of 10°C/min are shown in Figure 4. In the slow heating of the slowly cooled samples the recrystallization is clearly visible

in the presence of two endothermic peaks. The low temperature peak is due to melting of the originally present crystals, while the second peak corresponds to the melting of crystals formed by recrystallization during heating. The first peak is smaller than the second one because the first peak is partially annihilated by exothermic heat associated with the recrystallization. In the fast cooled samples there is only one high temperature melting peak because the melting peak associated with the original crystals, formed during cooling, is completely annihilated by the exothermic heat due to recrystallization, indicating that most –if not all- originally formed crystals recrystallize. Moreover even a slight increase of crystallinity can be observed at about 210°C during heating.

Less recrystallization is observed in the slowly cooled samples because when crystals have a high perfection and/or size, as occurs when cooled down slowly, their associated melting point is higher. At higher temperature the supercooling and therefore the (re)crystallization rate is lower and recrystallization is accordingly less complete during short time allowed at that particular supercooling. This explains the two peaks that are visible for the heat capacity in the slowly cooled samples during slow heating. From these measurements it can be concluded that the perfection of the crystals in the slowly cooled pCBT is higher than in the quenched (in this case cooling with 100°C/min) pCBT.

Figure 4: Results of the DSC measurement with a slow heating for both cooling rates. In the left graph the crystallinity is indicated and in the right the heat capacities.

From Figure 4 also the initial crystallinity, this is the crystallinity at room temperature (which is equal to the crystallinity at 150°C), can be compared. As can be seen, the value for the quenched samples is not significantly lower than the one of the slowly cooled samples. This means that the difference in crystal perfection and the amount of associated disordered polymer (including more tie-molecules between crystals) plays a predominant role in toughness improvement.

Measurements with fast heating

When the samples are heated at a rate of 100°C/min the recrystallization is less likely to occur because the time allowed at a given degree of supercooling is reduced. Experiments at such a rate give a clearer view on the quality and size of the original crystals because the first melting peak is less influenced by exothermic recrystallization heat. In Figure 5 the results of these measurements are presented. Clearly, after slow cooling a single melting peak is observed, which is due to the melting of the original

crystals, no exothermic recrystallization events are present. However, even with fast heating, recrystallization in the fast cooled samples cannot be suppressed completely as can be deduced from the bimodal character of the melting peak. This corresponds to a very low perfection of the crystals formed during fast cooling.

Obviously, as directly observed, crystallization during fast cooling occurs at lower temperatures, when the supercooling is high, and as a consequence the perfection of the crystals is poor. The crystallization and corresponding melting peak temperatures are indicated in Figure 6 for the measurements using the fast heating rate of 100°C/min. The crystallization temperature during fast cooling (179.2°C) is significantly lower than for the slow cooling (194.8°C). For the melting temperature this is vice versa. This is only possible because of recrystallization during heating at significantly higher temperatures compared to the crystallization temperature of the slow cooling experiment.

Figure 5: Results of the DSC measurement with a fast heating for both cooling rates. In the left graph the crystallinity is indicated and in the right the heat capacities.

Crystallinity of produced composites

The measurements mentioned above are all measured on pCBT without fibers in a DSC device. It is also important to measure the crystallinity of the produced composites. Therefore some samples from the composites produced with the two-step method are taken for DSC measurements. The samples are heated at a rate of 100°C/min. Note that a correction needs to be made for the presence of the fibers. The fiber mass fraction of the samples was accurately determined by TGA after the DSC experiments and the measured melting enthalpy was renormalized to the actual amount of pCBT present. In

Figure 6: Thermal cycles to which the samples are subjected with an indication of the melting temperatures (T_m) and the crystallization temperature (T_c) for the heating rates of 100°C/min.

the integration involved in determining the melting enthalpy, $c_{pa}(T)$ was approximated by an extrapolation from the melt, knowing that the $c_p(T)$ contribution of the fibers is linear over the entire temperature range of the experiments.

In Figure 7 the crystallinity of the samples is shown. At room temperature both samples have the same crystallinity, which means that in the production of composites the cooling rate does not influence the crystallinity. The melting point of the quenched sample is clearly higher than from the slowly cooled sample. This is clearly understandable from the results of the previous DSC experiments. Without these experiments this would have been unexpected because the quality of the crystals in the quenched samples should be lower, and therefore also the melting point, than in the slowly cooled samples.

Figure 7: Evolution of the crystallinity in produced composites, when heated up at a rate of 100°C/min.

However like discussed above a recrystallization occurs. When crystal perfection is poor pCBT can recrystallize, even when heated at a rate of 100°C/min. This recrystallization makes that the melting temperature of the quenched sample appears higher than the one of the slowly cooled composite.

Therefore it can be concluded that the crystals in the quenched composites are from a very low quality, compared to the slowly cooled samples. The goal of the quenching of the composites was to make the crystals less perfect, so the target is reached with the quenching after complete polymerization.

CONCLUSION

A non-isothermal production is possible with CBT. Therefore two different production techniques are developed which make it possible to produce composite plates. The first method is the prepreg method in which rovings are used, and the second method is the film stacking method. This last method is used when fabrics are used as reinforcement.

For the non-isothermal production two different cooling rates after complete polymerization are used: a slow cooling rate and quenching. From three point bending tests an increase in toughness can be observed after quenching. The fracture toughness Mode II test even indicate a twice as high crack propagation energy for the quenched samples compared to the slowly cooled samples.

The explanation for the higher toughness after quenching can be found in the crystal perfection. The slowly cooled as well as the quenched composites contain about the same amount of crystals, but in the case of the quenched samples the crystals contain a

lot more defects. These defects are in fact some amorphous material present in between the crystals. Therefore a higher amount of defects will give a higher toughness.

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